

WHAT MAKES YOU PRONE TO GET VARICOSE VEINS?

A **vein specialist** **fidi** is an expert who deals in the problem related to varicose and spider veins. These are ugly, bulging, and twisted veins that are obvious from the skin, and being one of the most common things out there it has various treatment alternatives available all you need to do is talk with the [vein doctor midtown](#).

What makes you prone to get varicose veins:

Aging particularly after 40+

Pregnancy

Premenstruation or contraceptive pills

Genetics

Obesity or sudden weight gain

An occupation that puts strain on veins.

When should you seek varicose vein treatment?

If you've tried various ways such as apple cider vinegar and other home remedies, or you are worried about the look of your legs or encountering severe symptoms you must consult the doctor.

What happens when you visit the doctor?

They make you stand, your doctor will check your legs, look for the signs of swelling veins. He or she may ask if you are dealing with any problems and what they sound like. Then, your doctor may do an ultrasound examination to see if the valves in your veins are as they should be or it has some buried ailments.

Veins Treatment NYC Options

Ultrasound-guided Foam Sclerotherapy and Endovenous Chemical Ablation- These procedures are the best to work and you can rely on these without any issue. It operates by treating the specific area of venous problems.

Ambulatory Phlebectomy is a method that eliminates large bumping out varicose veins. With this method, the unhealthy veins are picked up and skillfully extracted through very little incisions that don't even need stitches or anything else. This procedure is often a more proficient alternative to attend surface veins than practicing multiple sclerotherapy treatments.

Visual Sclerotherapy- this technique is commonly utilized to correct visible spider veins and small varicose veins that can be seen from the skin itself. A basic sclerosant is given into the veins, let them get reduced in size, close off and after a period of while it just vanishes. However, 2-5 applications are often required, but the effects are long-lasting.

One common problem that might irritate the issue even further and take beauty off is spider vein. Spider veins are related to varicose veins but they are not so thick. The signs of spider veins can be mitigated with a [spider vein treatment](#). They arrive on the legs and ankles as similar to the threads. Doctors estimate every third person is dealing with the pain of vein ailment and that is not something which has appeared in the recent year but presents for long ages.

Another common way to treat spider vein treatment is sclerotherapy. Sclerotherapy is the way of injecting veins with a liquid that creates the veins to deflate and disappear after some time. Sclerotherapy can be done without any preparation and typically has no downtime. One doesn't have to stay in the hospital or a clinic as this is done in an outpatient way. Using sclerotherapy is not a one-time thing as it could take anywhere from one to five sessions depending upon the severity of the ailment you have.